

Impact of Groove Design on Viscous Drag Reduction in Wet Clutch Lubrication for Energy-Efficient Power Transmissions

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This study investigates how radial groove design affects viscous drag in wet clutch lubrication films for energy-efficient automotive transmissions. Drag torque, defined as the torque generated due to the viscosity of the lubricant, is measured experimentally as a function of rotational speed (100–1500 rpm), accounting for aeration effects on film behaviour. CFD simulations complement the experimental analysis, which is conducted using a customized, low-cost, single-disc tester across varied film thicknesses (150–500 μm) and lubrication flow rates (0.01–1 lpm). The research quantifies how groove geometry and distribution alter the torque-speed relationship, revealing design strategies to minimize drag losses while maintaining the required torque capacity, which is proportional to the contact surface. By correlating simulated flow dynamics with experimental measurements, this work provides actionable insights for optimizing wet clutch energy efficiency. The results bridge fundamental hydrodynamics with practical transmission design, advancing energy-saving solutions for automotive powertrains.

Keywords: Wet clutch, viscous losses, drag torque, energy efficiency, grooves

INTRODUCTION

In modern automotive transmissions, improving energy efficiency remains a key challenge as regulatory and performance demands continue to rise. One significant contributor to energy losses in wet clutches is viscous drag torque, generated by the motion of rotating clutch plates submerged in lubricant [1]. During the open clutch state, where torque transfer is not required, this drag becomes a parasitic loss. As previous studies have shown, particularly in high-speed lubrication regimes, aeration, caused by air suction within the lubricant film, can dramatically alter film dynamics and reduce drag torque. However, the onset of this two-phase flow is strongly influenced by local geometrical features and operating conditions, making predictive modeling inherently complex. Experimental and computational studies have increasingly focused on understanding the interplay between lubricant film behavior, air suction, and energy dissipation mechanisms to guide design optimizations [2].

Among the many design variables affecting drag performance, surface texturing through groove patterns has emerged as a promising approach [3]. Prior investigations, including both experimental visualizations and CFD simulations, demonstrated that radial grooves can accelerate air suction into

the lubrication film, reducing the shear area and locally thickening the film. This dual mechanism enhances aeration onset and reduces drag, especially under conditions of high rotational speed and low flow rate. While early analytical models adequately describe flat-disc configurations, the complexity of multiphase flow in grooved geometries necessitates CFD-based and experimental analyses to fully capture the underlying physics. Building upon this framework, the present study explores how specific groove design parameters, such as number, width, and depth, influence viscous drag and lubrication film behavior, with the aim of identifying configurations that minimize energy losses while preserving torque capacity.

EXPERIMENTAL ASSESMENT OF DRAG TORQUE

The experimental assessment of drag torque was carried out using an open-clutch single-disc test rig designed to evaluate torque losses and flow visualization in a simplified disc pair configuration, one stationary and one rotating. Measurements were conducted across a range of angular velocities (100–1500 rpm) and clearances (150–500 μm), with key influencing parameters including lubrication flow rate, disc spacing, and groove geometry. The study identified three characteristic

operating zones depending on speed: a low-speed region with single-phase flow and linear torque increase, a mid-speed region with a torque drop due to two-phase flow effects, and a high-speed zone with torque rise from disc oscillations and impact phenomena. Representative results are shown in Fig. 1, illustrating the variation of drag torque with speed, and in Fig. 2, highlighting typical flow behavior captured during operation.

Fig.1. Measurement of drag torque vs speed, $N=10$, $h=150 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig.1. Flow visualization for $N=10$, $n=350 \text{ rpm}$ and $h=150 \mu\text{m}$ where flow remains single phase.

CFD ANALYSIS

CFD simulations were also carried out to gain further insights into the internal flow dynamics within the discs gap. The results, shown in the pressure contour plot in Fig. 3, reveal how the flow structure changes with varying rotational speeds. At lower speeds, the flow is primarily radial, with uniform temperature distribution. As speed increases, azimuthal pressure gradients develop, leading to the formation of high- and low-pressure zones and more complex flow patterns. These pressure variations significantly influence the onset

of two-phase flow, which becomes more prominent at higher speeds.

Fig.3. Pressure contour for $n=1000 \text{ rpm}$, $h=150 \mu\text{m}$.

CONCLUSIONS

This study explored the impact of groove geometry and operating conditions on viscous drag in open wet clutches, with a focus on enhancing energy efficiency in power transmissions. Experimental results highlighted how specific flow regimes, particularly the onset of two-phase flow, significantly influence torque losses. The presence of grooves was shown to affect pressure distribution and flow behaviour, contributing to drag reduction under certain conditions. Complementary CFD simulations offered further insight into internal flow mechanisms, revealing how groove-induced pressure gradients evolve with speed. Together, these findings underscore the potential of optimized groove design to minimize drag torque and improve overall transmission efficiency.

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